

1 **A switch in ZC3H12A and ZC3H12B in ectoderm lineage specification.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We describe here reciprocal changes in expression of alpha and beta genes of a zinc finger nuclear factor
8 encoded by the ZC3H12 family during a developmental transition. Induction of ZC3H12B occurred
9 concomitant with silencing of ZC3H12A at the point of specification of the germ layers, between the
10 pluripotent stem cell and the ectoderm. The same switch could be observed at mesoderm lineage
11 commitment.

12 Citations

13 1. Matsushita, K., Takeuchi, O., Standley, D.M., Kumagai, Y., Kawagoe, T., Miyake, T., Satoh, T.,
14 Kato, H., Tsujimura, T., Nakamura, H. and Akira, S., 2009. Zc3h12a is an RNase essential for controlling
15 immune responses by regulating mRNA decay. Nature, 458(7242), pp.1185-1190.